

Scheduled Caste Protest In Relation To Various Discriminations Made To Them in the Society

Author Details: Abhimanyu kumar: Asst.prof. Sociology, Govt. P.G. College, Ranikhet

Abstract: *In this paper I have shown an analysis of news items collected from secondary sources, i.e. the news paper and findings which have come out from this analysis. As we have said earlier that data for this study have also been collected form secondary sources. For collecting data we have selected Hindi News Papers Dainik Jagran and Amar Ujala for identifying events. I have collected the news cutting of various news items which are related to the scheduled caste protests in western U.P District (Meerut) during last Five years from 2005 to 2010. On the basis of these items we have made an effort to analyze the scheduled caste protest in Meerut District. We have found 100 news items based on 11 various issues such as land related cases, reservation policy cases, rape cases, corruption in development schemes, crop cases, and panchayat conflict touchers against scheduled caste, killing / Murder against scheduled caste conflicts beside these issues. We have also taken area of events as another variable, rural, semi urban and urban.*

Key words:- Newspapers, rural panchayat, corruption, reservation, untouchbilty, scheduled caste

INTRODUCTION: - The Government of India Act 1935 placed the ex-untouchables in a schedule and they were for the first time called scheduled castes. In 1936 British government of India ordered in specifying certain castes in the list of depressed classes as scheduled castes. The scheduled castes throughout the country occupy the lowest rank in the castes hierarchy. In the hierarchy of unequal relationships, the scheduled caste are at the bottom and hence socially inferior to all others in the community. (Murugkar, 1991).

Scheduled castes were one of the groups which were most backward. The basic determinants of scheduled caste status were untouchability and impure occupations, other determinants were their low economic, political and educational conditions. After independence, the scheduled caste (SCs) receives special mention in the constitution of India with special provisions in education, employment and political representation. Article 46 for instance declares. “The state shall promote with special care the programmer’s for educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people and in particular of the scheduled castes and scheduled tribes and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation. (Zelliot, 1992)

Meaning of Protest:

Protest is an attack on the prevailing system in an intellectual or organized way. Viewed against this is revolution which is a sickness in society, a breakdown of the social order, general demoralization and civil war protest is based on every man’s desire to be free. This feeling is above any reason, tradition and power. Protest per se is rather good or bad but it is an effective means of achieving social change and mobility in a modern society. It is doing be noted that most political and social change of twentieth century have been accelerated by various protest movement. Protests is necessary to maintain a fair rate of change in the face of entrenched interests in any society both to further the will of the majority and to attain equity for minorities. (Joseph, 1986:)

Charles Tiley’s (1978: 106-108) distinguishes four main components of protests.

1. The organization of the group or group involved protest movements are organized in many ways, varying from spontaneous formation of crowds to tightly disciplined revolutionary groups.
2. Mobilization this involves the ways in which a group acquires control over sufficient resources to make collective action possible. Such resources many include supplies of material good and political support.
3. The common interests of those engaging in collective action what they see as the gains and losses likely to be achieved by their policies or tactics. Some common interests always underlie mobilization to collective action.

4. Opportunity obviously chance events may occur that provide opportunities to pursue revolutionary aims. Many forms of collective actions, including revolution, are greatly influenced by such incidental happenings.

Singh(2000: 95-97) has discussed the protest ideology which not only articulates the new values and new goals but also unveils the structure of social inequalities and injustices found existing in the prevailing social order of the society and mobilize justification for the rejection of an unjust structure. The position of the untouchable within it and the strategies available to them for registering their protest and of seeking an effective share in the power structure of Indian society could perhaps provide a framework for developing a more generalized ideology of protest for sub national deprived groups.

The dalit protest a necessary outcome of an obscurantist Hindu tradition with its deep rooted prejudice against the Davits. It therefore, assumes that the movement is limited to achieving the objectives of advancement in socio-economic, civic and political fields within the exiting order without seeking a transformation of that society. (**Gopal Guru, 1993**)

Objectives under study

The objective under the study pertains to the numbers, various types and forms of protests by scheduled castes being observed in the recent years.

Research Methodology:

Area of Study:-

For the purpose of present study NCR Area of Meerut was selected as the area of study. The total area of the district according to the records is 3911 square miles. The total population of Meerut district in 241751, which is distributed as 132904 in rural area and 108848 in urban area. The population of scheduled castes in rural area is 287108 in urban areas is 161.694, thereby scheduled caste constitute larger segment of the total population in rural areas and in urban area. Thus the scheduled castes have been active in politics. They are artisans, workers, professionals, servicemen and there are several institutions and associations run by them.

Universe/Sample and Respondents:

The rural and urban area of the Meerut district would be the universe of our study. In the present study we have collected 100 news items from Dainik Jagran and Amar Ujala Hindi daily Newspapers Meerut edition during 2005-2010. 15 news items have been selected for detailed case study.

Methods of Data Collection and Analysis

At the first stage we have collected data of 100 events of protest by scheduled caste in Meerut district through two Hindi newspapers namely Amar Ujala and Dainik Jagran published from 2005to 2010. At the second stage 50 events were selected for Interview.

At the first stage data of 100 news items have been presented in the form of tables related to all variables and aspects related to every objective/question. Simple statistics, percentages and proportions have been presented in all tables and findings are arrived at. At the second stage 50 events have been presented in the form of table on nature and consequences of protests

Table:-1. Year Wise Distribution of Scheduled Caste protest in western U.P (2005 – 2010)

S.No.	Year	No. of News	Percentage
1.	2005	13	13 %
2.	2006	09	09 %
3.	2007	37	37 %
4.	2008	23	23 %
5.	2009	08	08 %
6.	2010	10	10 %
	Total	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that of the 100 events reported in the news items of 13 (i.e. 13 %) events have taken place in 2005, 09 (i.e. 09 %) in 2006, 37 (i.e. 37 %) in 2007, 23 (i.e. 23 %) in 2008, 08 (i.e. 08 %) 2009 and 10 (i.e. 10 %) in 2010. The table shows that the largest numbers of events of protests have taken place in 2007 and the minimum numbers of events of protests have taken place in 2009. Thus the year 2007 appears to be more important quantitatively for protests of the scheduled castes as largest number of events have been reported in this year. This needs further explanation on which will be undertaken later.

Area Wise Distribution

After the dividing of news items yearly, there is need to classify data in different sectors like the area or place of happening where they occur i.e. rural, urban and semi urban. Thus the area wise distribution of items has been presented as follows in the table.

Table.2: -Distribution of News Items of the Scheduled Caste Protest according to Area

(Rural Semi Urban, Urban) western U.P (2005 – 2010)

S.No.	Area	No. of Events	Percentage
1.	Rural	64	64 %
2.	Twon	14	14 %
3.	Urban	22	22 %
	Total	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that out of 100 news items 64 (i.e. 64 %) news items indicate that all events have taken place in rural area and 14 (i.e. 14 %) in town and 22 (i.e. 22 %) urban areas. Thus the fact suggests that the largest number of events reported from the rural areas. It means larger number of scheduled caste protests have taken place in rural areas.

Year and Area (Time and Place) of Events

Distribution of events in different sectors of society has been presented in the previous table. Now it is also necessary to know how many protests taken place in which year in different sectors. This has been presented in the following table.

Table 3: -Year and Area Wise Distribution of News Items of the Scheduled Caste

Protest in western U.P (2005 – 2010)

S.No.	Year	Rural	Town	Urban	Total	Percentage
1.	2005	06	03	04	13	13 %
2.	2006	07	--	02	09	09 %
3.	2007	23	09	05	37	37 %
4.	2008	16	02	05	23	23 %
5.	2009	06	--	02	08	08 %
6.	2010	06	--	04	10	10 %
	Total	31	14	22	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that out of 100 news items 13 (i.e. 13 %) news items in 2005, 06 are taken place in rural area, 03 in town and 04 from urban area. In the year 2006, 7 news items reported from rural area and only 2 from urban area. Out of 37 (i.e. 37 %) news items in 2007, 23 are taken place from rural area 09 in town and 05 in urban area. In the year 2008 of the 23 (i.e. 23 %) news items 16 are from rural area, 02 from town and 05 are taken place in urban area. In the year 2009 only 08 (i.e. 8 %) news items 06, are taken place from rural area and 02 are taken place in urban area. In the year 2010 of the 10 (i.e. 10 %) news items 06 are reported from rural area and 04 from urban area, no case from town. The above facts suggest that maximum news items reported in 2007 from rural area.

Issues of Events

Many scheduled caste protests have taken place during the period 2005 to 2010. These protests are different in their nature like killing, land dispute case, rape case etc. Nature wise distribution of protest among scheduled caste during last five years has been presented in the following table.

Table 4:-Distribution of News Items of the Scheduled Caste Protest according to nature of events in western U.P (2005 – 2010)

S. No.	Nature of Events	No. of Events	Percentage
1.	Land cases	19	19 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	08	08 %
3.	Rape cases	04	04 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	08	08 %
5.	Crop cases	01	01 %
6.	Punchayat conflict	01	01 %
7.	Torture cases against SCs	19	19 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	13	13 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	05	05 %
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	14	14 %
11.	Caste Conflict	08	08 %
	Total	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that out of 100 news items 19 (i.e. 19 %) events are related to land cases, 08 (i.e. 8 %) are related to reservation policy, 04 (i.e. 04 %) is rape cases, 08 (i.e. 08 %) related to corruption in development schemes, only 01 (i.e. 01 %) is crop case and 01 (i.e. 01 %) is punchayat conflict case, 19 (i.e. 19 %) torture cases, 13 (i.e. 13 %) conflict related to Ambedkar status. 05 (i.e. 05 %) events are related to physical violence, 14 (i.e. 14 %) cases are related to killing/murder, 08 (i.e. 08 %) events are caste conflicts.

Year Wise Events

The nature of these events is varying in every year. Now we classify the varying nature of events in the period of 2005 to 2010.

Table 5:- Year and Area Wise Distribution of Issues of Scheduled Caste Protest in western U.P (2005 – 2010)

S.No	Nature of Events	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	Total	%
1.	Land cases	05	01	06	05	—	02	19	19 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	02	—	02	02	01	01	08	08 %
3.	Rape cases	01	01	01	—	—	01	04	04 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	01	01	05	01	—	—	08	08 %
5.	Crop cases	—	—	—	01	—	—	01	01 %
6.	Punchayat conflict	01	—	—	—	—	—	01	01 %
7.	Torture cases against SCs	02	03	06	03	03	02	19	19 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	—	—	08	01	01	03	13	13 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	—	—	02	03	—	—	05	05 %
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	01	01	03	05	03	01	14	14 %
11.	Caste Conflict	—	02	04	02	—	—	08	08 %
	Total	13	09	37	23	08	10	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that of the 19 (i.e. 19 %) cases of land, 05 in 2005, 01 in 2006, 05 in 1998, no case in 2009 and 02 in 2010 have been taken place. Of the 08 (i.e. 08 %) reservation policy cases 02 in 2005, 02 in 2007, 02 in 2008, 01 in 2009 and only 01 case in 2010 has been presented. Of the 04 (i.e. 04 %) Rape cases 01 in 2005, 01 in 2006, and 01 in 2007. No case reported in 2008 and 2009, 01 hold in 2010. Of the 08 (i.e. 08 %) corruption in development schemes cases 01 in 2005, 01 in 2006, 05 in 2007, 01 in 2008, no case in the year 2009 and 2010. A case of punchayat conflict had been taken place in 2005. Of the 19 (i.e. 19 %) case of torture against SC 02 in 2005, 03 in 2006, 06 in 2007, 03 in 2009 and 02 in 2010 has been presented of the 13 (i.e. 13 %) conflict related to Ambedkar statues, 08 in 2007, 01 in 2008, 01 in 2009 and 03 in 2010 have been taken place of the 05 (i.e. 05 %) physical violence against SC, 02 in 2007, 03 in 2008, no case reported in the 2005, 2006, 2009 and 2010. Of the 14 (i.e. 14 %) cases killing/murder of SC 01 in 2005, 01 in 2006, 03 in 2007, 05 in 2008, 03 in 2008 and only 01 case in 2010. Of the 08 (i.e. 08 %) cases of caste conflict among SC 2 found in 2006, 04 in 2007, 02 in 2008, no case found in the year 2005, 2009 and 2010.

The above facts suggest that maximum (37 out of 100) events are found in the year 2007.

Area Wise Nature of Events

Scheduled caste protests are varying in their nature. The nature of protest also appear to depend on area or locality the nature of events in relation to areas of occurrence like rural, urban and semi urban are presented in the following table.

Table6:- Distribution of the events of Scheduled Caste Protest according to area (Rural, Semi Urban and Urban) in western U.P (2005 – 2010)

S.No.	Nature of Events	Rural	Town	Urban	Total	%
1.	Land cases	16	02	01	19	19 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	01	–	07	08	08 %
3.	Rape cases	03	–	01	04	04 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	02	02	04	08	08 %
5.	Crop cases	01	–	–	01	01 %
6.	Punchayat conflict	01	–	–	01	01 %
7.	Torture cases against SCs	11	05	03	19	19 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	10	–	03	13	13 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	04	01	–	05	05 %
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	12	01	01	14	14 %
11.	Caste Conflict	03	03	02	08	08 %
	Total	64	14	22	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that of the 19 (i.e. 19 %) Land cases 16 reported from rural area, 02 from semi urban, 01 from urban area 08 (i.e. 08 %) cases of reservation policy have 7 from urban area, 01 from Rural area, no case reported from town of the 4 (i.e. 4 %) rape cases 03 reported from rural area, only 01 from urban area. 8 (i.e. 8 %) cases of corruption in development schemes have 2 from Rural area, 02 from semi urban and 4 cases reported from urban areas. A single case which is related with crop and also panchayat conflict is reported from rural area. 19 (i.e. 19 %) cases of torture against SCs 11 reported from Rural area, 05 from semi urban and 03 from urban areas. 13 (i.e. 13 %) of conflict related to Ambedkar statues 10 reported from Rural area, and 03 from urban areas. 05 (i.e. 5 %) physical violence against SCs 04 from Rural area and only 01 from semi urban areas. 14 (i.e. 14 %) cases of killing / murder of SCs 12 reported from Rural areas, 01 from semi urban area and 01 from urban areas. 8 (i.e. 8 %) cases conflict cases of SCs 03 case reported from rural area and 03 from semi urban area and 02 from urban area.

Area Wise Events in Year 2005

Nature of these events has been presented in different sectors of society like (Rural, Town, and Urban). In the year 2005, separately present in the following table.

Table 7:- Distribution of the events of Scheduled Caste Protest in the year 2005 area wise to (Rural, Town and Urban) in western U.P.

S.No.	Nature of Events	Rural	Town	Urban	Total	%
1.	Land cases	04	01	01	05	05 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	02	02	02 %
3.	Rape cases	01	–	–	01	01 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	–	–	01	01	01 %
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Panchayat conflict	01	–	–	01	01 %
7.	Torture cases against SCs	–	01	01	02	02 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	–	–	–	–	–
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	–	–	–
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	–	01	–	01	01 %
11.	Caste Conflict	–	–	–	–	–
	Total	06	03	04	13	13 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2005, of the 5 (i.e. 5 %) land cases 04 from Rural area only 01 case from town area are reported. Only 2 (i.e. 2 %) reservation cases are reported from urban area. A single case which is related with rape reported from rural area and single panchayat conflict case which is related from rural area. 01 (i.e. 1 %) case of corruption in development schemes reported from urban area. Only 1 (i.e. 1 %) case of panchayat conflict related from rural area. 02 (i.e. 02 %) cases of torture against SCs 01 reported from semi urban area and 01 from urban area, a single case which is related with killing/murder of SCs reported from Rural area.

Area Wise Events in the Year 2006

Nature of these events has been presented in different sectors of society like (Rural, Town and Urban). In the year 2006, separate present in the table:-

Table 8:- Distribution of the events of Scheduled Caste Protest in the year 2006 area wise to (Rural, Town and Urban) in western U.P.

S.No.	Nature of Events	Rural	Semi urban	Urban	Total	%
1.	Land cases	01	–	–	01	01 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	–	–	–
3.	Rape cases	01	–	–	01	01 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	–	–	01	01	01 %
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	–
7.	Torture cases against SCs	03	–	–	03	03 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	–	–	–	–	–
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	–	–	–
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	01	–	–	01	01 %
11.	Caste Conflict	01	–	01	02	02 %
	Total	07	–	02	09	13 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2006, a single case (i.e. 1 %) which is related to land, reported from rural area. Only one case of rape, reported from rural area. Case of corruption in development schemes reported from urban area. Torture cases against SCs all 03 (i.e. 03 %) reported from rural area. Only one killing / murder case of SCs reported from rural area. 02 (i.e. 02 %) of case conflict case 01 reported from rural area and 01 reported from urban area. There is no case of reservation policy. Crop cases, panchayat conflict, conflict related to Ambedkar Statues, physical violence etc.

Area Wise Events in the year 2007

Nature of these events has been presented in different sectors of society like (Rural, Town and Urban). In the year 2007, separately present in the following table:-

Table9:- Distribution of the events of Scheduled Caste Protest in the year 2007 area wise to (Rural, Town and Urban) in western U.P

S.No.	Nature of Events	Rural	Town	Urban	Total	%
1.	Land cases	05	01	–	06	06 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	01	–	01	02	02 %
3.	Rape cases	–	–	01	01	01 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	01	02	02	05	05 %
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	–
7.	Torture cases against SCs	03	02	01	06	06 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	08	–	–	08	08 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	01	01	–	02	02 %
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	03	–	–	03	03 %
11.	Caste Conflict	01	03	–	04	04 %
	Total	23	09	05	37	37 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2007, of 06 (i.e. 6 %) Land case 5 reported from rural area 01 reported from town area. A single case which is related with rape reported from urban area. 05 (i.e. 5 %) cases of corruption in development schemes 01 reported from rural area 02 reported from semi urban area and 02 from urban area 06 (i.e. 6 %) cases which are related to torture against SCs 03 reported from rural area, 02 reported from semi urban area, only one case reported from urban area. All 8 (i.e. 8 %) conflict related to Ambedkar Statues are reported from rural area. Physical violence against SCs is reported 02 (i.e. 2 %) 01 from rural area and one from semi urban area, all 03 (i.e. 3 %) killing/murder of SCs are reported from rural area. 04 (i.e. 4 %) of cases conflict among SCs 01 reported from rural area and 3 reported from semi urban area.

Thus the above facts suggest that in the year 2007 more protest movements have taken place.

Area Wise Events in the Year 2008

Natures of these events have been presented in different sectors of society like (Rural, Town and Urban). In the year 2008, separately in the following table:-

Table 10:- Distribution of the events of Scheduled Caste Protest in the year 2008 area wise to (Rural, Town and Urban) in western U.P.

S.No.	Nature of Events	Rural	Semi urban	Urban	Total	%
1.	Land cases	04	–	01	05	05 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	02	02	02 %
3.	Rape cases	–	–	–	–	–
4.	Corruption in development schemes	01	–	–	01	01 %
5.	Crop cases	01	–	–	01	01 %
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	–
7.	Torture cases against SCs	01	02	–	03	03 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	–	–	01	01	01 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	03	–	–	03	03 %
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	05	–	–	05	05 %
11.	Caste Conflict	01	–	01	02	02 %
	Total	16	02	05	23	23 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2008, 5 (i.e. 5 %) land cases 4 reported from rural area and 01 from urban areas, all 02 (i.e. 2 %) cases which are related to reservation policy reported from urban area, a single case of corruption in development schemes reported from rural area. 01 (i.e. 1 %) crop case which is reported from rural area. Torture cases against SCs are 03 (i.e. 3 %) 01 from rural area 02 from semi urban area is reported. A single conflict related to Ambedkar statues reported from urban area, all 03 (i.e. 3 %) physical violence against SCs reported from rural area. 05 (i.e. 5 %) killing/murder of SCs reported from rural areas. 02 (i.e.2%) case which are related with caste conflict 01 reported from rural area and 01 is in urban area.

Area Wise Events in the Year 2009

Nature of these events has been presented in different sectors of society like (Rural, Town and Urban). In the year 2009, separately resent in the following table:-

Table11:- Distribution of the events of Scheduled Caste Protest in the year 2009 area wise to (Rural, Town and Urban) in western U.P.

S.No.	Nature of Events	Rural	Semi urban	Urban	Total	%
1.	Land cases	–	–	–	–	–
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	01	01	01 %
3.	Rape cases	–	–	–	–	–
4.	Corruption in development schemes	–	–	–	–	–
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	–
7.	Torture cases against SCs	03	–	–	03	03 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	01	–	–	01	01 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	–	–	–
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	02	–	01	03	03 %
11.	Caste Conflict	–	–	–	–	–
	Total	06	–	02	08	8 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2009, 01 (i.e. 1 %) reservation policy case which is related from urban area has been reported. All 03 (i.e. 3 %) torture cases against SCs reported from rural area. A single conflict related to Ambedkar status reported from rural area. Killing / murder of SCs is 03 (i.e. 3 %), 02 reported from rural area, 01 from urban area.

Area Wise Events in the Year 2010

Nature of these events has been presented in different sectors of society like (Rural, Town and Urban). In the year 2009, separately present in the following table:-

Table 12:- Distribution of the events of Scheduled Caste Protest in the year 2010 area wise to (Rural, Town and Urban) in western U.P.

S.No.	Nature of Events	Rural	Semi urban	Urban	Total	%
1.	Land cases	02	–	–	02	02 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	01	01	01 %
3.	Rape cases	01	–	–	01	01 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	–	–	–	–	–
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	–
7.	Torture cases against SCs	01	–	01	02	02 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	01	–	02	03	03 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	–	–	–
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	01	–	–	01	01 %
11.	Caste Conflict	–	–	–	–	–
	Total	06	–	04	10	10 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2010, 02 (i.e. 2 %) land case which is related from rural area have been reported. Only 01 (i.e. 1 %) reservation case reported from urban area. A single case which is related with rape reported from rural area. Torture cases against SCs only 02 (i.e. 2 %) reported 01 from rural area and 01 from urban area. 03 (i.e. 3 %) conflict related to Ambedkar statues, 01 reported from rural area and 02 from urban areas. A single case of killing/murder reported from rural area. There is no case of corruption in development schemes, crop cases, panchayat conflict, physical violence against SCs, caste conflict etc.

Scheduled Caste Protests and Concern Authorities

Here are presenting 100 scheduled caste protest based on various issues such as rape, murder, land case etc. before different government and semi-government authorities such as District Magistrate, S.D.M Panchayat etc. in the following table:-

Table 13:-Protests of Scheduled Castes and Concern Authorities in western U.P (2005 – 2010)

S. No	Authorities Concerned	Total	percentage
1.	District Magistrate	24	24 %
2.	S.D.M	08	08 %
3.	Police Administration	52	52 %
4.	Development Officers	08	08 %
5.	Panchayat	03	03 %
6.	State Government / C.M	05	05 %
	Total	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005– 2010)].

The above table shows that of the 100 cases, 24 (i.e. 24 %) cases are presented before district magistrate, 08 (i.e. 08 %) are presented before S.D.M, 52 (i.e. 52 %) before police administration, 08 (i.e. 08 %) before development officers, 03 (i.e. 03 %) presented before panchayat and 05 (i.e. 05 %) before state government and chief minister. The above fact suggested that maximum cases are presented (52 out of 100) before police administration.

Year Wise Distribution with the Concern Authorities

Here we presenting 100 protest of scheduled caste, based on various issues such as rape, murder, land cases etc. before different government authorities such as District Magistrate, S.D.M Panchayat etc. in tabular from following table consist yearly data presentation from 2005 to 2010:-

Table14:-Year Wise Distribution of Scheduled Caste Protest with the Concern Authorities in western U.P (2005 – 2010).

S.No	Authorities Concerned	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	Total	%
1.	District Magistrate	03	03	06	05	01	06	24	24 %
2.	S.D.M	01	—	05	01	01	—	08	08 %
3.	Police Administration	05	05	20	14	05	03	52	52 %
4.	Development Officers	01	01	02	03	—	01	08	08 %
5.	Panchayat	02	—	01	—	—	—	03	03 %
6.	State Government / C.M	01	—	03	—	01	—	05	05 %
	Total	13	09	37	23	08	10	100	100 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that of the 24 (i.e. 24%) cases which are presented before District Magistrate, 03 in 2005, 03 in 2006, 06 in 2007, 05 in 2008, 01 in 2009 and 06 in 2010. 08 (i.e. 08%) cases which are presented before S.D.M 01 in 2005, no cases in 2006, 05 in 2007, 01 in 2008, 01 in 2009, no case presented concern Authorities. 52 (i.e. 52%) cases which are presented before police administration 05 in 2005, 05 in 2006, 20 in 2007, 14 in 2008, 05 in 2009, 03 in 2010. 08 (i.e. 08%) cases which are presented before development officer 01 in 2005, 01 in 2006, 02 in 2007, 03 in 2008, no case in 2009, 01 in 2010. 03 (i.e. 03%) cases which are presented before panchayat 02 in 2005 and 01 in 2007, no case presented in the year 2006, 2008, 2010 before panchayat. 05 (i.e. 05%) cases which are presented before state government and chief minister 01 in 1995, 03 in 2007, 01 in 2009, no case presented before State Government and Chief Minister in the year 2006, 2008 and 2010.

Events and Authority

There are 100 protests of scheduled caste have been taken out in the year (2005 – 2010) from Meerut District. These protests are in different nature and against the various authorities. The nature and authority wise distribution of protests are distributed in the following table.

Table 15:- Events & Authority wise Distribution of protests during in western U.P (2005 – 2010)

Authorities									
S.No	Nature of Events	D.M	S.D.M	Police Administration	Devp. officer	Panchayat	State Govt./CM	Total	%
1.	Land cases	05	01	13	–	–	–	19	19 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	01	–	04	01	01	01	08	08 %
3.	Rape cases	02	–	02	–	–	–	04	04 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	–	–	–	07	–	01	08	08 %
5.	Crop cases	–	–	01	–	–	–	01	01 %
6.	Punchayat conflict	01	–	–	–	–	–	01	01 %
7.	Torture cases against SCs	05	04	10	–	–	–	19	19 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	05	03	04	–	–	01	13	13 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	05	–	–	–	05	05 %
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	02	–	11	–	01	–	14	14 %
11.	Caste Conflict	03	–	02	–	01	02	08	08 %
	Total	24	08	52	08	03	05	100	100%

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that of the out of 19 (i.e. 19%) cases of land 05 are presented before SDM and 13 before police administration. Out of 08 (i.e. 08%) reservation policy cases only one presented before district magistrate, 04 presented before police administration, 01 before Development officer 01 before panchayat 01, before State Government. Out of 04 (i.e.04%) Rape case 02 presented before District Magistrate and 02 are presented before police administration. Out of 08 (i.e. 08%) corruption in development schemes cases 07 presented before development officer and only one case presented before state government. A single crop case (i.e. 1%) presented before police administration and also a single panchayat conflict (i.e.1%) presented before District Magistrate of the 19 (i.e. 19%) cases of torture against SCs. 5 presented before District Magistrate, 4 are presented before SDM, 10 presented before police dministration; of the 13 (i.e. 13%) conflict related to Ambedkar statues cases, 05 presented before District Magistrate, 03 before SDM, 04 before police administration and only 01 presented before state Government. 05 (i.e. 05%) physical violence against SCs all are presented before police administration killing/murder of SCs is 14 (i.e. 14%), 02 presented before District Magistrate, 11 presented before police administration; of the 08 (i.e. 08%) caste conflict cases 03 presented before District Magistrate, 02 presented before police administration, 01 presented before panchayat and 02 before state Government. The above fact suggests that maximum (52 out of 100) events are presented before police administration.

Events and Authority in 2005

There are 13 protests of scheduled castes have taken out in 2005 in Bulandshaer District. These protests are in different nature and against the various authorities, the nature and authority wise distribution of protests are presented in the following table:-

Table16:- Protests events and related Authority in the year 2005.

Authorities									
S.No	Nature of Events	D.M	S.D.M	Police Administration	Devp. officer	Panchayat	State Govt./CM	Total	%
1.	Land cases	02	–	02	–	–	01	05	05 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	01	–	01	–	02	02 %
3.	Rape cases	–	–	01	–	–	–	01	01 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	–	–	–	01	–	–	01	01 %
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	01	–	01	01 %
7.	Torture cases against SCs	01	–	01	–	–	–	02	02 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	–	01	–	–	–	–	01	01s %
11.	Caste Conflict	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
	Total	03	01	05	01	02	01	13	13 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2005, of the 5 (i.e. 5 %) land cases 02 presented before District Magistrate, 02 are presented before police administration. Of the 02 reservation policy cases 01 presented before police administration and 01 presented before panchayat. A single (i.e.1 %) rape case presented before police administration. Corruption in development schemes is only one (i.e. 1 %) is presented before development officer panchayat conflict is only (i.e. 1 %) is presented before panchayat. Of the 02 (i.e. 2 %) torture cases 01 presented before District Magistrate and 01 before police administration. Only 01 (i.e. 1 %) case of killing / murder of SCs is presented before SDM.

Events and Authority in 2006

There are 09 protests of scheduled castes have taken out in 2006 in Bulandshaer District. These protests are in different nature and against the various authorities. The nature and authority wise distribution of protests are presented in the following table:-

Table17:- Protests events and related Authority in the year 2006.

Authorities									
S.No	Nature of Events	D.M	S.D.M	Police Administration	Devp. officer	Panchayat	State Govt./CM	Total	%
1.	Land cases	–	–	01	–	–	–	01	01 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
3.	Rape cases	–	–	01	–	–	–	01	01 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	–	–	–	01	–	–	01	01 %
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	01	–	01	01 %
7.	Torture cases against SCs	02	–	01	–	–	–	03	03 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	01	–	–	–	–	–	01	01 %
11.	Caste Conflict	–	–	02	–	–	–	02	02 %
	Total	03	–	05	01	–	–	09	09 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2006, a single case (i.e. 1%) which is related to land presented before police administration, only one (i.e. 1%) rape case presented before police administration, 01 (i.e. 1%) case of Corruption in development schemes presented before development officers. Of the 03 (i.e. 3 %) torture cases against SCs 02 presented before District Magistrate and 01 before police administration. A single (i.e. 1 %) case of killing / murder of SCs are presented before district magistrate. Of the 02 (i.e. 2%) caste conflict cases is presented before police administration.

Events and Authority in 2007

There are 37 protests of scheduled castes have taken out in 2007 in Bulandshaer District. These protests are in different nature and against the various authorities. The nature and authority wise distribution of protests are presented in the following table:-

Table18:- Protests events and related Authority in the year 2007.

Authorities									
S.No	Nature of Events	D.M	S.D.M	Police Administration	Devp. officer	Panchayat	State Govt./CM	Total	%
1.	Land cases	–	–	06	–	–	–	06	06 %
2.	Reservation policy cases	–	–	02	–	–	–	02	02 %
3.	Rape cases	–	–	01	–	–	–	01	01 %
4.	Corruption in development schemes	03	–	–	02	–	–	05	05 %
5.	Crop cases	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
6.	Punchayat conflict	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
7.	Torture cases against SCs	01	02	03	–	–	–	06	06 %
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar status	01	03	03	–	–	01	08	08 %
9.	Physical violence against SCs	–	–	02	–	–	–	02	02 %
10.	Killing / Murder of SCs	–	–	03	–	–	–	03	03 %
11.	Caste Conflict	01	–	–	–	–	01	02	02 %
	Total	06	05	20	02	01	03	37	37 %

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2007, of 06 (i.e. 6%) land cases all are presented before police administration. Of the 2 (i.e. 2%) reservation policy cases presented before police administration. A single rape case (i.e. 1%) presented before police administration. Of the 05 cases of corruption in development schemes. 03 presented before district magistrate and 02 presented before development officers. Of the 06 (i.e. 6%) torture cases of S.C. 01 presented before district magistrate 02 before S.D.M., 03 presented before police officers. Conflict related to Ambedkar Statues 08 (i.e. 8%) 1 presented before district Magistrate, 3 before S.D.M., 03 before police administration. 01 before state government. Of the 02 (i.e. 2%) physical violence against S.C. presented before police administration. All 03 (i.e. 3%) cases of killing/murder of S.C. is presented before police administration. Of the 02 (i.e. 2%) caste conflict cases 01 presented before district magistrate and 01 before panchayat.

Events and Authority in 2008

There are 23 protests of scheduled castes have taken out in 2008 in Bulandshahar district. These protests are in different nature and against the various authorities. The nature and authority wise distribution of protests are presented in the following table.

Table19:-Protests Event and related Authority in the Year 2008.

S. No.	Nature of Events	Authority						Total	%
		D.M.	S.D.M.	Police Administration	Deve Officers	Panchayat	State/Govt. C.M.		
1.	Land cases	01	01	02	01	--	--	05	5%
2.	Resevation policy cases	--	--	01	01	--	--	02	2%
3.	Rape cases	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
4.	Corruption in development schemes	--	--	--	01	--	--	01	1%
5.	Crop cases	--	--	01	--	--	--	01	1%
6.	Panchayat conflict	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
7.	Torture cases against S/Cs.	--	--	03	--	--	--	03	3%
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar statues	01	--	--	--	--	--	01	1%
9.	Physical violence against S/Cs.	--	--	03	--	--	--	03	3%
10.	Killing/Murder of S/Cs.	01	--	04	--	--	--	05	5%
11.	Caste Conflicts	02	--	--	--	--	--	02	2%
	Total	05	01	14	03	--	--	23	23%

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)]

The above table shows that in the year 2008, out of 5 (i.e. 5%) land cases 01 presented before district magistrate, 01 before S.D.M., 01 before police administration, 01 before development officers. Of the 02 (i.e. 2%) reservation policy cases 01 presented before police administration, 01 before development officers. A single (i.e. 1%) corruption in development scheme is presented before development officers. Only one (i.e. 1%) crop case is presented before police administration. All 03 (i.e. 3%) torture against S.C. is presented before police administration. A single (i.e. 1%) conflict related to Ambedkar statues is presented before district magistrate. All 03 (i.e. 3%) physical violence cases is presented before police administration. Of the 05 (i.e. 5%) killing/murder case 01 presented before district magistrate, 04 before police administration. All 02 (i.e. 2%) caste conflict cases presented before district magistrate.

Events and Authority in 2009

There are 08 protests of scheduled castes have taken out in 2009 in Bulandshahar district. These protests are in different nature and against the various authorities. The nature and authority wise distribution of protests are presented in the following table.

Table20:-Protests Event and related Authority in the Year 2009.

S. No.	Nature of Events	Authority						Total	%
		D.M.	S.D.M.	Police Administration	Deve Officers	Panchayat	State/Govt. C.M.		
1.	Land cases	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
2.	Resevation policy cases	--	--	--	--	--	01	01	1%
3.	Rape cases	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
4.	Corruption in development schemes	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
5.	Crop cases	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
6.	Panchayat conflict	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
7.	Torture cases against S/Cs.	01	--	02	--	--	--	03	3%
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar statues	--	01	--	--	--	--	01	1%
9.	Physical violence against S/Cs.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
10.	Killing/Murder of S/Cs.	--	--	03	--	--	--	03	3%
11.	Caste Conflicts	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
	Total	01	01	05	--	--	01	08	8%

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2009, 01 (i.e. 1%) reservation policy case is presented before state government. Of the 03 (i.e. 3%) torture cases against S.C. 01 (i.e. 1%) presented before district magistrate, 02 presented before police administration. A single (i.e. 1%) case of Ambedkar statues is presented before S.D.M. All 03 (i.e. 3%) cases of killing/murder are presented before police administration.

Events and Authority in 2010

There are 10 protests of scheduled castes have taken out in 2010 in Bulandshahar district. These protests are in different nature and against the various authorities. The nature and authority wise distribution of protests are presented in the following table.

Table21:-Protests Event and related Authority in the Year 2010.

S. No.	Nature of Events	Authority						Total	%
		D.M.	S.D.M.	Police Administration	Deve Officers	Panchayat	State/Govt. C.M.		
1.	Land cases	01	--	--	01	--	--	02	2%
2.	Resevation policy cases	01	--	--	--	--	--	01	1%
3.	Rape cases	01	--	--	--	--	--	01	1%
4.	Corruption in development schemes	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
5.	Crop cases	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
6.	Panchayat conflict	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
7.	Torture cases against S/Cs.	--	--	02	--	--	--	02	2%
8.	Conflict related to Ambedkar statues	03	--	--	--	--	--	03	3%
9.	Physical violence against S/Cs.	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
10.	Killing/Murder of S/Cs.	--	--	01	--	--	--	01	1%
11.	Caste Conflicts	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
	Total	06	--	03	01	--	--	10	10%

Source: Dainik Jagran & Amar Ujala [Daily Newspapers, Hindi (2005 – 2010)].

The above table shows that in the year 2010, 2 (i.e. 2%) land cases 01 presented before district magistrate, and 01 is before development officers. A single (i.e. 1%) reservation policy case is presented before district magistrate. All 02 (i.e. 2%) torture cases against S.C. are presented before police administration. Of the 03 (i.e. 3%) conflict related to Ambedkar statues are presented before district magistrate. A single (i.e. 1%) killing/murder case of S.C. are presented before police administration.

Conclusion/Result: - We have found 100 news items based on 11 various issues such as land related cases, reservation policy cases, rape cases, corruption in development schemes, crop cases, and panchayat conflict touchers against scheduled caste, killing / Murder against scheduled caste conflicts beside these issues. We have also taken area of events as another variable, rural, semi urban and urban. We have also presented the record of six concerned authorities like District Magistrate, S.D.M. police administration, development officer, state government, chief minister and panchayat against whom the protests have been held. An analysis of these items (events) is presented here shows that the largest numbers of events of protests have taken place in 2007 and the minimum numbers of events of protests have taken place in 2009. Thus the year 2007 appears to be more important quantitatively for protests of the scheduled castes as largest number of events have been reported in this year. In the year 2010, 2 (i.e. 2%) land cases 01 presented before district magistrate, and 01 is before development officers. A single (i.e. 1%) reservation policy case is presented before district magistrate. All 02 (i.e. 2%) torture cases against S.C. are presented before police administration. Of the 03 (i.e. 3%) conflict related to Ambedkar statues are presented before district magistrate. A single (i.e. 1%) killing/murder case of Scheduled caste are presented before police administration.

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